

ARIES

Accelerator Research and Innovation for European Science and Society
Horizon 2020 Research Infrastructures GA n° 730871

DELIVERABLE REPORT

Pushing back the charge frontier

DELIVERABLE: 18.5

Document identifier:	ARIES-D18.5
Due date of deliverable:	End of Month 54 (October 2021)
Report release date:	30/11/2021
Work package:	WP18:Very High Gradient Acceleration Techniques
Lead beneficiary:	CNRS
Document status:	Final

ABSTRACT

The beam charge in laser-plasma accelerators is about 2 orders of magnitude lower than in conventional accelerators. This is a major bottleneck, which hinders the development of these accelerators and their applications. Here we report on several strategies to increase the beam charge. First, we present a new technique to dechirp the electron beam and thus increase the spectral density of charge. Second, we report on a numerical optimization of density transition injection and present new target designs that aimed at producing higher charge with a better stability. We also present a numerical study on the increase of the charge in the 1-10 MeV range. We then describe laser defects that can reduce the beam charge, and we propose solutions to fix them. Lastly, we report on a new method for guiding the laser that increases the conversion efficiency of the laser to the electron beam.

ARIES Consortium, 2021

For more information on ARIES, its partners and contributors please see <http://aries.web.cern.ch>

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 730871. ARIES began in May 2017 and will run for 4 years.

Delivery Slip

	Name	Partner	Date
Authored by	C. Thaury, Task coordinator	CNRS	29/11/2021
Edited by	C. Thaury, Task coordinator	CNRS	29/11/2021
Reviewed by	A. Specka, WP coordinator	CNRS	29/11/2021
Approved by	M. Vretenar on behalf of the Steering Committee		30/11/2021

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. INTRODUCTION	4
2. ENERGY CHIRP COMPENSATION	6
3. OPTIMIZATION OF INJECTION	7
3.1. NUMERICAL OPTIMIZATION OF DENSITY TRANSITION INJECTION	8
3.2. NEW TARGET DESIGN	9
3.2.1. <i>Double nozzle setup</i>	10
3.2.2. <i>Shock nozzle</i>	11
4. OPTIMIZATION OF THE CHARGE BELOW 10 MEV	12
5. LASER OPTIMIZATION	14
6. ACCELERATION IN A LASER-GENERATED WAVEGUIDE	15
7. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE PLANS	17
8. REFERENCES	18
ANNEX: GLOSSARY.....	19

Executive summary

We explored different strategies to increase the density of charge of electron beams produced by laser-plasma acceleration and more generally the energy conversion efficiency from the laser to the electron beam.

Laser-plasma accelerators produce generally electron beams with a large energy spread. This large spread is mainly due to the energy chirp introduced during the injection and acceleration processes. We proposed and demonstrated a technique to reduce the beam chirp at the end of the accelerator and hence increase the spectral density of charge by about a factor of 3.

The second area of improvement identified concerns the injection of electrons into the accelerator field. We first conducted a numerical study to enhance the charge that can be trapped via density-transition injection. We then developed innovative targets that should allow us to achieve this density transition with an improved stability. More recently, we focused on the optimization of the charge below 10 MeV for applications such as industrial radiography or radio-biology.

We also evaluated the effect of several laser imperfections (pulse-front curvature, 4th order spectral phase, pulse front tilt). Different strategies for correcting these defects have been proposed and implemented.

Lastly, we developed an all-optical technique to guide the laser which drives the accelerator and we combined it with the density transition injection technique. It allows us to significantly increase the energy of the electron beams and hence the conversion efficiency from the laser to the beam.

1. Introduction

The beam charge in laser-plasma accelerators is about 2 orders of magnitude lower than in conventional accelerators; for instance, few hundreds of MeV electron beams have typical charge density about 1 pC/MeV and at best about 10 pC/MeV. This low charge is a major bottleneck of laser-plasma accelerators, which hinders the development of applications. It questions in particular the pertinence of using laser-plasma accelerators for high energy physics. In the recent years, several techniques have been developed to control the injection of electron bunches into laser-plasma accelerators and produce electron beams with a few MeV energy spreads and normalized emittance lower than 1 micrometer. Yet, none of these techniques can produce electron beams with a good quality and a charge exceeding 10 pC per MeV. We report here on different strategies for increasing the density of charge and more generally on techniques for enhancing the energy transfer from the laser to the electron beam.

For most applications the relevant parameter is not the beam charge but the spectral density of charge per solid angle (unit [pC/MeV/mrad²]). Indeed, the relatively large energy spread (above a few % at best) and the large divergence (usually several mrad) of electron beams from laser-plasma accelerators are critical issues for beam transport. Increasing the total charge may therefore be useless if it is accompanied by an increase in energy spread or emission angle. It is also well documented that, at first order, the charge increases as the laser energy. An appropriate figure of merit to compare

the performance of laser-plasma accelerators at a given energy is therefore the spectral density of charge per solid angle and laser Joule. Table 1 shows that, at the beginning of the project, the density of charge obtained with various injection techniques and 100 TW class-lasers, in the 100s MeV range, was about $N \sim 0.1 \text{ pC/MeV/mrad}^2$ per laser Joule. It also shows that the most loaded beams are the ones with the largest energy spread and divergences. As an example, the high charge (300 pC) obtained in Ref. [3] could be difficult to handle for applications requiring a beam transport. Such beams are however well adapted to produce X-ray radiation through Bremsstrahlung for applications that can cope with large energy spreads and divergences such as industrial radiography. Conversely, applications requiring a beam transport necessitate the use of beams with a large charge density N , and therefore low energy spread and divergence, such as the ones obtained in Ref. [1].

Table 1: Typical performance of laser-plasma accelerators in the 100s MeV range.

Injection technique and Ref.	Laser energy	Beam energy	Energy spread FWHM	Charge	Divergence FWHM	$N \text{ [pC /MeV/ mrad}^2 \text{ /J]}$
Colliding injection [1]	1J	180 MeV	1.3%	11 pC	3 mrad	0.5
Density transition injection [2]	0.77 J 1.2 J	130 MeV 50 MeV	5 % 11 %	1.2 pC 90 pC	3 mrad 10 mrad	0.02 0.16
Self-truncated ionization inj. [3]	2.5 J	250 MeV	14 %	300 pC	7 mrad	0.07

In 2020, one order of magnitude higher charge density was reported in Ref. [4], using density transition injection. The reported beam had a charge of 123 pC, an energy spread of 15% and a divergence of 0.85 mrad. It was produced from a 2 J laser leading to $N = 7 \text{ pC /MeV/ mrad}^2$. Compared to [1] the gain comes mainly from the low beam divergence (the solid angle is 12 times smaller than in [1]), while the spectral density of charge is similar in both cases ($\sim 5 \text{ pC/MeV/J}$). The reason for this unprecedented low beam divergence at this energy was not identified.

Here, we report on different strategies for increasing the charge density and more generally the energy conversion efficiency from the laser to the electron beam. First, we propose an original approach to reduce the beam energy spread. Second, we present a detailed numerical study of density transition injection (the technique used in Refs. [2] and [4]) which aims to identify the best laser and target features to increase the beam charge. We also propose new schemes to achieve this injection. We then report on the optimization of the charge below 10 MeV for industrial applications and on the influence of a few laser defects on the beam charge. We finally discuss a new technique for guiding the laser and thus increasing the energy conversion efficiency.

2. Energy chirp compensation

Like most of the properties of the electron beam, the energy spread is largely determined at the time of injection. However, this parameter is not completely fixed afterwards. In a laser-plasma accelerator, the plasma wave which is formed behind the laser propagates at the group velocity of the laser v_g , while the electron bunch which is highly relativistic propagates at a speed very close to that of light in vacuum ($v_e \sim c$). Therefore, the electron bunch tends to overtake the laser during the acceleration process. The electrons injected last are therefore located behind the electrons already accelerated. This induces a relationship between the electron position and energy. In a first approximation, this relation can be described by a linear drift (or "chirp") α . In that case, the energy spread of the beam is $\Delta E \sim \sigma_z \times \alpha$, where σ_z is the length of the electron bunch. It is thus possible, in principle, to reduce the energy spread by suppressing this drift.

In practice, we can act on this drift by exploiting another consequence of the speed difference between the laser and the electron bunch. This difference causes the electrons to move progressively from the accelerating to the decelerating region of the wakefield. This phase shift is best known as one of the main limits to the energy gain in laser-plasma accelerator, but as a side effect, this phase shift also reduces the energy spread of the beam. This is because during the dephasing process, the electrons at the front of the bunch begin to decelerate, while the electrons at the back continue to gain energy. If the length of the plasma accelerator is carefully chosen, this effect can, at least partly, compensate for the linear drift in energy. Yet, it can be complex to precisely adjust this length, and in any case, this technique lacks of degrees of freedom to really control the dechirping. We have thus proposed a new method to control the dechirping of the beam.

The technique is inspired by the one used to produce a steep density gradient for density transition injection [2]. The idea is to use a hydrodynamic shock to create an over-density, with a very steep transition, at the exit of the accelerator. This overdensity allows the acceleration of the tail of the electron bunch, while the front is less accelerated and then decelerated. Adjusting the position of the hydrodynamic shock, longitudinally and vertically, allows to tune the position and the amplitude of the overdensity and thus to optimize the dechirping [5]. This approach was tested during an experiment with the *Salle Jaune* laser facility at LOA. The main results are presented in Fig. 1. The top panel shows the density profile used, as well as the spectra obtained with or without the overdensity. These data illustrate that the charge per MeV is increased by a factor of 2 to reach 6 pC/MeV, while the energy dispersion is reduced to less than 10%. The total charge is about 120 ∓ 20 pC and the beam divergence 8 ∓ 3 mrad. The spectral density of charge is thus comparable to the state of the art [1-4], but similar to Ref. [3], the angular charge density remains low because of a large beam divergence. An important point here is that the beam divergence is not increased during the energy-chirp compensation (it is also 8 ∓ 3 mrad in the reference case). The use of the same technique, but starting from a low divergence beam should allow the production of very high-density beams. More generally this study shows that plasma engineering appears as a new tool to manipulate the properties of an electron beam. In Sec. 3, a similar plasma shaping is used to control the injection of electrons into the accelerating field.

Fig. 1 Energy-chirp compensation. Top panel, density profile with (red) and without (blue) the overdensity. Bottom panel, corresponding spectra, averaged over 10 shots. The coloured areas indicate the standard deviation.

3. Optimization of injection

The injection of the electron bunch into the accelerating field is the most critical step in a laser-plasma accelerator because it impacts all the beam properties (divergence, energy dispersion, charge, stability, pointing). It requires to locally heat electrons from the plasma to inject them into the wakefield. Several injection techniques (e.g. [1-3]) have been developed to control this injection. Here we focus on density transition injection [2] which is relatively simple to implement and has led to the highest angular density of charge produced so far from a laser-plasma accelerator [4].

This technique requires a plasma density profile with locally a very steep density gradient. Typically, the density should decrease by a factor of about 2 over a few tens of micrometers, and then remain constant over several centimeters. As the plasma wavelength increases with a decreasing density, the density down-ramp induces a slowing down of the back of the accelerator cavity (the cavity lengthens). This phenomenon reduces the minimum speed for an electron to be trapped. Thus, the injection will preferentially occur at the time when the speed of the cavity is minimal. The injection is thus localized, which induces the acceleration of an electron beam with a reduced energy dispersion.

Here we present a numerical optimization of the density transition and then report on a new target design.

3.1. NUMERICAL OPTIMIZATION OF DENSITY TRANSITION INJECTION

In this section, we discuss the results of a series of particle in cell (PIC) simulations where the density transition height, the downramp length, and the normalized laser amplitude a_0 are systematically varied, to show how the electron beam parameters are affected by these parameters [6]. The main results are displayed in Figs 2-4.

Fig. 2 Beam charge as a function of the density transition height K , the downramp length and a_0 .

In Fig. 2, the charge is observed to be maximum for higher density transition (large K) and short downramp lengths. The explanation is simple: sharper density gradients lead to a stronger slowing down of the wakefield and hence to a more efficient injection. The charge also increases with the laser energy. This growth is much stronger than expected; while in general the charge increases linearly with the laser energy, here the charge can increase up to 3 times more. Physical effects explaining this increase are discussed in Ref. [6]. Figures 3 and 4 illustrate the influence of these parameters on the beam energy spread and transverse emittance. It appears that the increase of the charge with the laser energy goes along an increase of the energy spread and emittance. For instance, for $K=1.7$ and a downramp length $L=20 \mu\text{m}$, the charge increases by a factor of 4 when the laser energy is multiplied by 1.6, but at the same time the energy spread is multiplied by 4 and the transverse emittance by 2. As a result, while the charge significantly increases, the spectral density of charge remains constant, and the spectral brightness N is significantly decreased. Therefore, increasing the laser intensity could be useful for application requiring a high total charge but not a high beam quality. Conversely, an intensity closer to the injection threshold is recommended if the beam as to be transported. In all cases, the highest spectral charge density and brightness are obtained for the sharpest and strongest density gradients (even if the use of longer ramp tends to reduce the emittance).

Fig. 3 Beam energy spread as a function of the density transition height K , the downramp length and a_0 .

Fig. 4 Normalized emittance as a function of the density transition height K , the downramp length and a_0

3.2. NEW TARGET DESIGN

Producing the very sharp density gradients required to get high charge-density beams is an experimental challenge. A successful technique consists in placing a sharp blade in a supersonic gas jet to create a hydrodynamic shock. The density profile of the plasma thus obtained presents a very steep gradient at the shock location with a density that decreases by a factor of about 2 over a few

tens of microns. A drawback of this technique is that the shock features can change shot-to-shot leading to significant shot-to-shot variations of the charge and spatial properties of the electron beam. Here we investigate alternative target designs for improving this stability.

3.2.1. Double nozzle setup

The first idea was to use two gas jets: one ultra-short (<1 mm) for the injection and a second much longer (> 3 mm) for the acceleration. A first preliminary experiment has been carried out at CEA Saclay in collaboration with Sandrine Dobosz. A 250 μm nozzle was used for the injection and a 3 mm one for the acceleration. There was an angle of 90° between the two gas flows. This setup did not allow us to control the injection. Indeed, the reflection of the gas flow of the second nozzle on the first one resulted in the formation of hydrodynamic shocks which perturbed the laser-plasma interaction. Moreover, the ultrashort nozzle was damaged after a few dozen of shots.

Following this first experiment, we run a series of simulations with the commercial software ANSYS. We mainly simulated the combination of a 500 μm long gas jet for the injection and a 5 mm long one for the acceleration stage. Simulations confirm the importance of the angle between the two jets. The obtained density profile for an angle of 60° is shown in Fig. 5. The density ratio between the two regions is $K \sim 3$ and the gradient length $L \sim 150 \mu\text{m}$. We use this setup in an experiment at LOA with the *Salle Jaune* laser system delivering 800 mJ on target. A spectrum obtained during this experiment is shown in Fig. 6. The beam quality was remarkably good with a measured energy spread of $\sim 2\%$, a divergence of 2 mrad, but a charge in the peak of only 0.1 pC. The density of charge per laser J was thus $N \sim 0.07 \text{ pC/mrad}^2/\text{J}$, similar to the ones measured in previous density transition injection experiments at LOA.

Fig. 5 Simulated density profile for the two-nozzle setup.

In a second experiment with larger laser energy (1.5 J) we obtained much higher charge and electron energy (350 MeV), but also with larger energy spread and beam divergence, so that the charge density was not increased. In both cases, the stability was not improved compared to experiments using a blade to create the density transition. On the contrary this stability was even worse due to the interaction between the two gas flows.

Fig. 6 Picture of the setup (left) and electron spectrum obtained with the two-nozzle setup (right).

3.2.2. Shock nozzle

As the interaction between the two gas flows is a major bottleneck in achieving stable injection, we developed a new target design, using a single nozzle. It is based on the concept of shock nozzle recently proposed at LOA [7]. The idea is to use a supersonic nozzle with a straight wall that reflects the gas flow on one side of the nozzle exit. We designed a 10 mm long rectangular nozzle and tested it in Fluent simulations. The main result is shown in Fig.7. The straight wall is visible on the left of the figure (gray square). It reflects the gas to generate a region of higher density with a sharp density gradient. The density then remains almost constant for about 10 mm.

Fig. 7a Two-dimensional density map of the 10 mm long shock nozzle. The vertical axis corresponds to the height above the nozzle exit, while the horizontal axis corresponds to the laser propagation axis.

This nozzle was manufactured in fused silica by a team from the Center for Physical Sciences and Technology at Vilnius, Lithuania and then tested at *Salle Jaune*. The measured plasma density profile in the shock region is displayed in Fig. 8. The density ratio is much smaller than expected ($K \sim 1.4$ compared to $K \sim 1.8$ in simulations). The gradient is thus shallower than expected from simulations. This weak gradient was not sufficient to control the injection of electrons into the wakefield. Moreover, we observed that this long highly supersonic nozzle has a tendency to deteriorate after a few hundreds of shots. We observed a similar behavior with a 20 mm long metallic nozzle but were not able to identify clearly the origin of the degradation (pollution or laser/plasma ablation).

Fig. 7b Measured density profile in the density transition region.

To conclude this section, none of the investigated schemes allowed to improve the performances of density transition injections. The best technique to achieved density transition injection, in the 100 MeV range, remains therefore the use of a blade to partly obstruct the gas flow and create a hydrodynamic shock, as first demonstrated in [2].

4. Optimization of the charge below 10 MeV

Low beam energy spread and divergence are mandatory for many experiments, notably those requiring beam transport but some applications can tolerate or even take advantage of a large divergence. It is in particular the case of industrial radiography for non-destructive testing. In this application the electron beam is converted to a large divergence X-ray beam via Bremsstrahlung, and then used to detect discontinuities in dense and thick objects. For radiation protection a cost issues, industrial companies are mostly interest in electron beams of less than 10 MeV. In the framework of ARIES, we started a study aiming at producing high-charge beams for this application.

We started from a systematic numerical study using PIC simulations. We considered a nitrogen plasma with a Gaussian density profile and a full width of 500 μm . The laser energy was varied between 0.1 and 0.7 J and the plasma density between $0.5 \times 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ and $9.5 \times 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-3}$. The main results are shown in Fig. 8. Most accelerated electrons are trapped into the wakefield through ionization injection. The charge below 10 MeV is observed to increase with the plasma density before saturating for densities larger than $6.5 \times 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-3}$. A similar behavior is observed for the total charge (including electrons above 10 MeV). The charge also strongly increases with the laser energy to reach $\sim 20 \text{ nC}$ for a 0.7 J laser pulse (the total charge in this case is 25 nC). The

variation of the charge with the laser energy is almost linear up to 0.4 J, while the trend is less pronounced for higher energies. These trends impact the energy transfer efficiency which reaches about 16% for a density $n_e \geq 6.5 \times 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ and a laser energy $0.2 \leq E \leq 0.4 \text{ J}$, before decreasing for higher laser energies. The corresponding mean energy of the electron beam is about 4.5 MeV and the spectral density of charge exceeds 35 nC/MeV for a 0.2 J laser energy. The physical effects explaining these trends are still under analysis.

Fig. 8 Charge below 10 MeV (left) and energy transfer efficiency to electron below 10 MeV (right) as a function of the pulse energy and plasma density.

The performance in terms of beam charge, spectral density of charge and transfer efficiencies is impressive. An experiment is planned to confirm them. The price to pay for this impressive charge is a very large divergence (up to 350 mrad); the angular-spectral density per laser joule is therefore only $N=1.5 \text{ pC/MeV/mrad/J}$. Nevertheless, given the very different features of the beams, a direct comparison with the state of the art in the 100 MeV range is daring. Moreover, this large divergence is not a drawback for the targeted applications.

5. Laser optimization

In Sec. 3, we reported on density transition experiments at LOA leading to a charge density of $N \sim 0.1$ pC/mrad²/J. This performance is comparable to the results obtained in most previous experiments and notably in [2], but more than one order of magnitude lower than the value recently reported in [4]. The changes that led to this impressive progress are not discussed in [4]. The fact that the density of charge per laser joule at LOA is a factor of two lower than the one that was obtained before an upgrade of the laser facility in 2012, made us suspect that a laser issue could explain, at least in part, this relatively low charge. We considered three different laser defects: pulse front curvature, pulse front tilt and spectral phase.

We first proposed a simple technique for determining the pulse-front-curvature (PFC) and pulse front tilt (PFT) of the laser [8]. We measured a pulse front curvature of 2.3 fs/cm² and a negligible pulse front tilt. A chromatic doublet lens of infinite focal length was developed to remove this defect [8]. Average electron spectra with or without this correction are shown in Fig. 9.

Fig. 9 Example of electron spectra without (top) or with (bottom) pulse-front-curvature correction.

Without correction the peak energy averaged over 20 shots is 152.2 \pm 23.9 (sd) MeV, and the charge above 45 MeV = 42.41 \pm 4.57 (sd) pC. With correction, the peak energy averaged over 17 shots is

193.9 +/- 22.0 (sd) MeV, and the charge above 45 MeV = 90.97 +/- 11.95 (sd) pC. Beam charge and peak energy are therefore significantly higher with PFC correction, corresponding to an increase of the energy transfer efficiency by almost 3. Nevertheless, as this increase goes along an increase of the energy spread, while the divergence remains constant at ~4 mrad, the charge density is not improved. This study will be continued in order to characterize and correct higher order spatio-temporal couplings. Note that the chromatic doublet used for PFC correction can also be used to tune PFT. We were therefore able to observe the strong effect of PFT on the trapped charge and confirm that the amount of PFT of our laser chain was negligible.

In a second experiment we studied the effect of the laser spectral phase on the electron beam properties. The effect of 2nd order phase (chirp) on laser-plasma acceleration is well known and routinely optimized. We investigated on the effect of 3rd and 4th order phases. Our measuring device of the spectral phase (SPIDER) was modified to measure the 4th order phase and we used a DAZZLER system to vary both 3rd and 4th orders. The optimum for the beam charge was obtained for 3rd and 4th order phases of zero. The small amount of 4th order which was present on the laser before optimization was observed to have a negligible effect on the electron beam properties. Therefore, the optimization of the spectral phase did not result in any gain.

6. Acceleration in a laser-generated waveguide

A last strategy for increasing the energy transfer efficiency was implemented. The idea here is to guide the laser pulse that drives the accelerator in order to increase the acceleration length and thus the transfer efficiency. This guiding has been performed for about 15 years using a capillary discharge, but this technique is only fully mastered at Berkeley lab. As a drawback, encapsulating LPA in a capillary severely limit the means to control electrons injection, but also exposes such device to optical damage. We proposed to use another technique where the waveguide is formed using a second laser pulse. The principle of the technique and the first demonstration of guiding were reported in [9]. It was then used for laser-plasma acceleration at the *Salle Jaune* laser facility. The setup is shown in Fig. 10a. A first laser pulse (P2) is focused over a line by an axiparabola to create the waveguide. A second ultra-high intensity laser pulse is focused into this waveguide to drive the plasma accelerator. It was then guided in the plasma channel shown in Fig. 10b. Electrons were injected through density transition injection. The transition was produced by using a blade to partly obstruct a 15 mm long rectangular H₂ gas jet. Due to pointing fluctuations, efficient guiding was observed for only 70% of the shots, but each successful shot led to the production of an electron beam with a peaked spectrum and an energy exceeding 600 MeV. These pointing fluctuations led also to a significant variation of the laser energy coupled into the wakefield and thus of fluctuations of the electron-beam charge.

Fig. 10 Laser-plasma guiding. (a) Experimental setup. (b) Transverse plasma density profile with or without the waveguide (P2). (e) Raw electron spectra with or without the waveguide. (f) Corresponding focal spots

Fig. 11 Series of 10 electron spectra sorted by charge

Figure 11 shows 10 spectra extracted from a series of 14 shots. A clear correlation between the beam energy and beam charge is observed and attributed to beam loading. The conversion efficiency is about 1% for GeV beams and 6% for the most loaded ones (e.g., the 65 pC shot shown in Fig. 11). The charge density N is about 0.06 pC/MeV/mrad²/J for best shots, similar to Ref. [2-3] but at a much higher beam energy (1 GeV compared to 130-250 MeV). It should be noted that if the density is lower

than that reported in Ref. [4] it is only because of a greater divergence (3 mrad vs 0.85 mrad). Note also that the density of charge is almost 10 times larger than the density obtained at 220 MeV with the same facility without guiding. The method appears therefore as a promising way to increase the beam charge.

7. Conclusion and future plans

In conclusion, among the different strategies implemented to increase the charge, only two were clearly successful: energy chirp compensation and laser guiding. Energy chirp compensation allowed to increase the charge density by a factor of 2. Laser guiding allowed to increase the charge density by one order of magnitude compared to previous experiments at LOA, while multiplying the energy by 3. Regarding density-transition injection, we identified in simulations the optimum parameters for increasing the charge density but we did not succeed in reproducing these parameters in an experiment. Moreover, the two new schemes developed to improve the stability did not give the expected results. Laser optimization study was a half-success, as it led to an increase by a factor of 3 of the energy conversion efficiency, but without any increase of the charge density.

These studies will be continued in different directions. Regarding, energy chirp compensation, the challenge is now to demonstrate this technique starting from a beam with a higher charge-density. However, no such experiment is planned at LOA at this time.

The laser optimization will be extended to the study of the influence of higher order spatio-temporal-couplings. We will also continue to develop innovative targets, both for improving the injection (charge density and stability), and for increasing the beam energy. This target optimization will be studied in the H2020 project *IFAST* (Task 6.3).

The numerical study aiming at increasing the beam charge below 10 MeV will be continued in the H2020 project *MULTISCAN 3D*. It will be followed by experiments which will benefit from the knowledge and expertise developed to create innovative targets in *ARIES* and *IFAST* projects.

Finally, the next objective regarding laser-plasma guiding is to upscale the setup on a PW laser facility to produce high-quality electron beams in the multi-GeV range. This project may use targets developed in *IFAST*. I will also benefit from a support from the H2020 project *LASERLAB* (JRA PRISES).

8. References

References in bold correspond to paper acknowledging ARIES.

- [1] C. Rechatin, J. Faure, A. Ben-Ismaïl, J. Lim, R. Fitour, A. Specka, H. Videau, A. Tafzi, F. Burgy, and V. Malka
Phys. Rev. Lett. **102** 164801 (2009)
- [2] A. Buck, J. Wenz, J. Xu, K. Khrennikov, K. Schmid, M. Heigoldt, J. M. Mikhailova, M. Geissler, B. Shen, F. Krausz, S. Karsch, and L. Veisz
Phys. Rev. Lett. **110**, 185006 (2013)
- [3] J. P. Couperus, R. Pausch, A. Köhler, O. Zarini, J. M. Krämer, M. Garten, A. Huebl, R. Gebhardt, U. Helbig, S. Bock, K. Zeil, A. Debus, M. Bussmann, U. Schramm and A. Irman
Nature Communications **8**, 487 (2017)
- [4] J. Götzfried, A. Döpp, M. F. Gilljohann, F. M. Foerster, H. Ding, S. Schindler, G. Schilling, A. Buck, L. Veisz, and S. Karsch
Phys. Rev. X **10**, 041015 (2020)
- [5] A. Döpp, C. Thauray, E. Guillaume, F. Massimo, A. Lifschitz, I. Andriyash, J.-P. Goddet, A. Tafzi, K. Ta Phuoc, and V. Malka
Phys. Rev. Lett. **121**, 074802 (2018)
- [6] F. Massimo, A. F. Lifschitz, C. Thauray, and V. Malka,
Plasma Physics and Controlled Fusion **60**, 034005 (2018)
- [7] L. Rovige, J. Huijts, A. Vernier, I. Andriyash, F. Sylla, V. Tomkus, V. Girdauskas, G. Raciukaitis, J. Dudutis, V. Stankevici, P. Gecys, J. Faure
arXiv:2103.12408 (2021)
- [8] A. Kabacinski, K. Oubrerie, J.-P. Goddet, J. Gautier, F. Tissandier, O. Kononenko, A. Tafzi, A. Leblanc, S. Sebban and C. Thauray
J. Opt. **23** 06LT01 (2021)
- [9] S. Smartsev, C. Caizergues, K. Oubrerie, J. Gautier, J.-P. Goddet, A. Tafzi, K. Ta Phuoc, V. Malka and C. Thauray
Optics Letters **44**, 3414 (2019)
- [10] K. Oubrerie, A. Leblanc, O. Kononenko, R. Lahaye, I. A. Andriyash, J. Gautier, J.-P. Goddet, L. Martelli, A. Tafzi, K. Ta Phuoc, S. Smartsev, and C. Thauray
Controlled acceleration of GeV electron beams in an all-optical plasma waveguide
Submitted (2021)

Annex: Glossary

Acronym	Definition
FWHM	Full Width at Half Maximum
PIC	Particle In Cell
LOA	Laboratoire d'Optique Appliquée
PFC	Pulse Front Curvature
PFT	Pulse Front Tilt
LPA	Laser Plasma Accelerator